

Emerging Open Science Leadership Fellows

Summary and scope

Open science practices, while gaining significant traction in Europe and North America, are still not common in many scientific communities and global regions. Many excellent resources and initiatives exist, however this existing work is often tailored to the pace and cultural norms of existing open science communities (European Union, United States, Canada, and scientific disciplines who have been early adopters). The pace, starting point, and work cultures of existing open science programs/capacity building efforts are not tailored to the work culture and knowledge bases of emerging open science communities. As a result, current open science efforts unintentionally exclude entire regions from the international open science movement, hampering the speed and effectiveness of global research. We have all experienced how global scale infectious disease can spread to impact millions of lives in a period of weeks. Early sharing of research and data led to faster vaccines and treatments, yet the practices and tools that enable sharing and collaboration are not accessible to all.

To build global research capacity, we seek to build open science communities of practice outside Western Europe, United States, and Canada. This proposal leverages the access and expertise of Code for Science & Society (CS&S), Open Life Science (OLS), MetaDocencia, and Talarify. The four orgs (based in UK, US, Argentina, and South Africa, respectively) **will collaborate to build a fellowship program that recruits and hosts regional leaders to scope, design, and execute initiatives that will have success introducing and deepening open science practices within regional scientific communities.** This work will leverage the community of practice model and the effectiveness of open science practices to develop the research capacity in global regions pivotal to research over the next ten years.

Overview of proposed work

Our experience in investing in, developing, and sustaining communities of practice has shown that transformative change must be locally led and internationally supported. We propose to develop a fellowship program that supports fellows to scope, design, and execute initiatives that will have success introducing and deepening open science practices within regional scientific communities. To support the creation of lasting regional capacity in research, we will support fellows to employ communities of practice, peer learning, and co-design models effectively. We believe that our international collaboration is well-positioned to leverage the expertise of not only our own organizations but that of sector partners to build a solid foundation of support for regional fellows to build global research capacity. (Examples of our sector partners: OpenScapes, Reproducibility for Everyone, Research Software Alliance, Invest in Open Infrastructure, The Carpentries, Academic Data Science Alliance, CSCCE, PREreview, SPARC, TTC Africa, among others.)

This proposal leverages the relative access and expertise of OLS, CS&S, MetaDocencia, and Talarify. The four orgs will recruit, host, and support regional research leaders as they scope, design, and execute initiatives that they feel will have success introducing their communities to open science practices or deepening the range and scope of those practices within their wider scientific communities. We're looking at Spanish-speaking South America and Anglophone Africa as the regions to pilot the program in 2022-2024.

MetaDocencia and Talarify will lead the recruitment process of regional research leaders with the experience and the interest in deepening open science in their communities. These fellows will assist in developing the mechanisms to recruit two cohorts of fellows – one focused on Spanish-speaking South America and one focused on Anglophone Africa. These fellows will be compensated to deliberate, design, scope, and execute a capacity-building program for open science specific to their region and the blockers they see their communities facing within it.

MetaDocencia and Talarify will build on their standing in their communities in identifying and recruiting fellows and in working with them to network map, scope challenges, identify areas for maximum impact. OLS and CS&S will provide mentorship and development support for the recruited fellows and work with them as they design and execute the programs they propose. The four orgs will draw on each others' strengths to:

- 1) Build an inclusive outreach program for recruitment that is cognizant of how local power dynamics are often overlooked in multi-national collaborations;
- 2) Design a transparent communication flow to keep communities engaged and abreast of the work;
- 3) Resource fellows with tools they need – including prototypes, inter and intra regional networking as well as co-facilitated sessions for visioning and idea development;
- 4) Support fellows in execution of the programs they design – including volunteer and contractor engagement, technical infrastructure for in person and hybrid meetings, development and translation of written documentation, et al;
- 5) Develop sustainability plans - including governance, documentation, and financial strategies for each initiative.

We propose the following phases to construct a 2 year fellowship program, outlined below:

Phase 1: Recruit and Research

- Develop and launch recruitment processes that are maximally inclusive
- Recruit and onboard 2 cohorts of regional research scientist/technologist fellows who represent regions where open science practices are nascent and impact potential is high
- Work with fellows to map the needs of their community
- Work with fellows to design a capacity-building program specific to their locale
- Fellows know from the start they will have a budget and time to develop and execute the program they design.

In year one, OLS, CS&S, MetaDocencia, and Talarify will identify leads to help build out 2 regional cohorts of fellows engaged in research from 2 underserved regions in Anglophone

Africa and Latin America. Recruiting may happen by invitation, nomination, and/or by open call in regional languages. It is important that this recruiting process happens in coordination and with significant input from the selected lead. We know from our experience running programs and soliciting open calls for submissions and nominations that these practices can be unintentionally exclusionary without co-design from local communities.

Mentored by OLS, CS&S, MetaDocencia, and Talarify, selected fellows will be paid to spend a portion of their time conducting research, comparing notes, and brainstorming local solutions to challenges of access and onboarding into open science practices and communities. They might consider who has access to education and institutional spaces; work cultures within them; what languages are used; what technical affordances are missing, inadequate, unreliable, underutilized; larger social, political, and cultural dynamics of which open science is a part in the region; and so on. After an initial scoping period, each cohort of fellows will design an onboarding program designed to intervene in their specific landscape and address a single one of the identified challenges.

Phase 1 Deliverables:

1. Recruitment and development of the first cohort of fellows
2. Landscape analysis of regional communities, intersections with global research community, unique needs, specific blockers
3. Designs of two capacity-building programs specific to research capacity in each region

Phase 2: Build and Grow

- Partner with fellows to launch local initiatives
- Grow local, regional, national, and international connections and attention for these projects
- Report on early impact and iterate in response to blockers
- Deeper work on communications, governance, fundraising to develop sustainability plans for each local initiative

In year two, CS&S, OLS, MetaDocencia, and Talarify will assist each regional cohort in executing the onboarding program they have designed, including extensive mentoring in network building and maintenance to build local/regional/nation momentum towards long term sustainability. The onboarding program may be a sequence of workshops, trainings, convenings; curricula, resources, writing, tools; internships and fellowships; conferences or other networking opportunities; or something else entirely. Fellows will have the discretion to decide and design their program.

CS&S, OLS, MetaDocencia, and Talarify will work to support the two cohorts to help them build on the experiences of other capacity building efforts in open science, non-profits, open technology, and related sectors, with the aim of building local communities with global reach.

Phase 2 Deliverables:

1. Launch of capacity-building programs

2. Engagement plan for regional communities: Building on the landscape analysis, a plan for growing local, regional, national and international engagement
3. Initial assessment of how the designed programs are working, including places for iteration and feedback
4. Sketches for communication design, project governance, fundraising for each initiative

Project outcomes

In order to conduct research more efficiently, inequality and imbalance in global research communities must be addressed. Disproportionately, communities in the Global South provide data to researchers from the Global North. The benefits of this research rarely feed back equally into researched communities. Building capacity for local research is a direct outcome of strengthening open science communities in selected regions in this proposal. By building paths for professionalization for scientists in South America and Africa, funders for this project will support the collaborating orgs to invest in a more equitable, global scientific community.

Anticipated outcomes include:

1. Visibility of open scientific communities in these locales with insight into the specific blockers scientists face advancing their work. This is a necessary part of the recruiting of fellows into the cohort program and will also identify and scope other potential areas for investment.
2. Individuals in Spanish-speaking Latin America and Anglophone Africa will have been introduced to open science practices.
3. Communities in these regions will have had the opportunity to build out open science infrastructure.
4. OLS, CS&S, MetaDocencia, and Talarify will have new findings to report about collaboratively developing capacity for open science internationally and in these regions.

Additional elements

Diversity, equity, & inclusion

Open science practices are still not common in many scientific communities and global regions. Many excellent resources and initiatives exist, however this work is often tailored to the pace and cultural norms of existing open science communities (European Union, part of North America, and certain scientific disciplines who have been early adopters). Our work in four continents, intervening at different points in the pipeline of open science infrastructure development, has shown us that international efforts to build capacity or expand the reach of open science practices are often culturally out of touch, technically and legally out of reach, or politically out of the question. At the local level, scientists lack consistent resources to push for the wholesale adoption of open science practices on their own. Our collective track record of work building capacity in the open science ecosystem around the world suggests that the expansion of open science practices must be locally led and internationally supported.

Our proposal seeks to support exactly such a collaboration, building on the track record of two established initiatives in the US and UK (CS&S and OLS) and two established initiatives in the identified regions MetaDocencia (Spanish-speaking Latin America) and Talarify (Africa). We will use our respective experiences to empower a set of leaders to identify and address a specific blocker to open science adoption. We are committed to recruiting fellows in the most inclusive way possible, including but not limited to nominations, word of mouth, directed calls, invitations to submit, etc. We are committed to hosting and supporting fellows at competitive rates to carry out the programs they design.

Risks and mitigation strategies

Risk 1: Collaboration is difficult.

While the four organizations are familiar with each others' work and some of us have worked together directly, we have not executed a four-way collaboration on this scale with each other. As soon as this project is funded, we will be developing an infrastructure for communication and workflow to make sure each team gets what they need; remains abreast of the others' work; is communicating regularly. We will invest early on in communication and documentation to build trust necessary for collaboration of this scale to succeed.

Risk 2: Fellow recruitment turns up a list of the usual suspects.

In our initial discussions, we have already discussed power dynamics that prevent scientists in these regions from self-nominating, applying, or otherwise feeling interpellated to participate in international programs. Our four orgs are committed to co-designing, with local communities, calls for participation in the fellowship program that will provide opportunities for a diverse *to each locale* cohort of open science leaders. MetaDocencia and Talarify will work with recruited fellows to recruit and decide on cohort membership.

Risk 3: Fellows are unable to actually dedicate time despite compensation because of other structural issues

We are committed to paying fellows for their time. At the same time, we recognize that a single paid intervention, even one that is competitive internationally, may still not be enough to overturn and undo structural issues around labor, care, and professional service. We are committed to co-facilitating engagements with fellows that are flexible and accessible to demands we may not be able to foresee at the present time. One of the underlying principles of this proposal is that our four orgs do not have the answers but are in a position to build the infrastructure to support those who can come up with solutions. This applies to how we structure the day-to-day work as well as our hopes for its outcomes.

Risk 4: Fellows' designs are not implementable

In order to avoid a scenario where at the end of year 1, fellows have designed programs that are out of scope, scale, or mission, we will work regularly with each cohort at intervals throughout the year. It is important to protect time when fellows discuss alone, discuss with their communities, discuss with regional partners. Our social infrastructure will include exchange between cohorts and with all four orgs from the start.

Sustainability strategy

The model of work we are proposing is innovative in that it uses the established credentials and infrastructure of established orgs to support research, design, and execution within, for, and by under-resourced communities of scientists. This program builds a temporary infrastructure aimed to significantly transfer resources while retaining local autonomy. If it is successful, we expect both local and international institutions will be interested in contributing to and supporting this work. Part of the work of supporting the fellows in year two of the grant is thinking with them about further programming and financial strategy to support it.